

Terpenes of Plant Origin and Their Modulating Activity on Multidrug Resistance in Human Breast Cancer Cell Lines: A Review Article

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ABSTRACT

The global burden of cancer increased to 18.1 million new cases and 9.6 million deaths in 2018, an alarmingly high number. Among the different types of cancer, breast cancer is one of the most common among the population, causing 11.6% of cancer deaths worldwide (WHO, 2018; Bray et al. 2018). It is one of the cancers with the greatest tendency to become multidrug resistant (MDR), which causes 90% of failures in the treatment of carcinomas. MDR is a phenomenon of resistance in tumors to chemically unrelated anticancer drugs and is one of the most formidable challenges in the field of chemotherapy. The most common mechanism is the expulsion of cytotoxic drugs through ABC (ATP-Binding Cassette) transporters. Among these, the most studied are P-glycoprotein (P-gp), multidrug resistance protein 1 (MRP1), and breast cancer resistance protein (BCRP). Therefore, the search for transporter inhibitors has gained importance, mainly in the use of natural products, among which terpenes stand out, as they have been shown to have powerful inhibition of MDR. This review describes studies with terpenes and their derivatives in breast cancer cell lines. Among *in vitro* models, the MCF-7 cell line is the most commonly used model. Active compounds were found: 2 monoterpenes, 6 sesquiterpenes, 15 diterpenes, 6 triterpenes, and 4 tetraterpenes, with diterpenes being the most studied as MDR modulators. The findings suggest that terpenes hold significant potential as effective MDR modulators, which could lead to improved chemotherapy outcomes in breast cancer treatment.

Keywords: Drug resistance, breast cancer, terpenes, P-gp, MRP1, BCRP, chemotherapy.

INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer is the most commonly diagnosed cancer in women, accounting for 24.2% of cases. In Mexico, 571,000 deaths were reported due to this cancer in 2016, making it the leading malignant neoplasm for the female population in the country (WHO, 2018; WHO, 2017; Bray et al. 2018). Various factors, such as age, lifestyle, breast injuries, hormonal treatments, and genetics, can increase the risk of developing breast cancer. The latter factor is attributed to 85-90% of breast cancer cases. The disease generally originates in the cells of the lobules

or ducts, and less frequently, it can arise in the stromal tissues (fatty and fibrous connective tissues of the breast). Four molecular subtypes of breast cancer have been defined: hormone-dependent tumors (or luminal, further classified into luminal A and B), tumors with amplification of the HER2 oncogene, and so-called triple-negative tumors. The luminal phenotype accounts for 65% of cases (HER2 negative with hormone receptor positive), 18-20% have HER2 receptor overexpression, and the remaining 15% are triple-negative (HER2 negative with hormone receptor negative) (Martin et al. 2015).

The success of breast cancer treatment depends on three key factors. The first is early diagnosis, as this directly influences the patient's prognosis. For patients in stage I (small tumors without axillary metastases), the 5-year survival rate is 95%; for stage II (tumors larger than 2 cm with moderate axillary metastases), it is 80%; for stage III (large tumors with skin or pectoral muscle involvement or massive axillary involvement), it is 60%; and for stage IV (distant metastases), the 5-year survival expectancy is only 25% (Martin et al. 2015). The second factor is the specific molecular subtype of the tumor, as this determines the appropriate treatment approach.

Finally, it is crucial to prevent and diagnose cases of multidrug resistance (MDR), as 90% of chemotherapy failures are currently attributed to the invasion and metastasis of drug-resistant cancers (Mansoori et al. 2015). MDR is a leading cause of morbidity and mortality in cancer and remains a challenge in treatment. The risk of tumors acquiring resistance to chemotherapy is a significant obstacle to the successful treatment of various cancer types (Clynes 2013). Cancer cells become resistant by reducing the activity of drugs, making MDR a serious problem in cancer treatment. The main challenge in chemotherapy is to administer a dose that maximizes efficacy and minimizes toxicity, but in the presence of MDR, higher drug doses are often required, leading to greater adverse effects on the patient without eliminating the cancer. MDR is thus an important factor in the failure of many chemotherapy regimens. It can occur in a variety of human cancers, and in the case of breast cancer, it frequently arises during the treatment of advanced carcinoma. Different cellular and molecular mechanisms leading to the development of a resistant phenotype have been reported, including efflux through ABC transporters, which is a known drug resistance mechanism in cancer cells. Some MDR mechanisms involve the overexpression of transmembrane proteins such as P-gp, MRP1, and BCRP, which can expel a wide range of xenobiotics from cells, including vinca alkaloids, podophyllotoxins, anthracyclines, taxanes, and kinase inhibitors. This mechanism protects cancer cells from

first-line chemotherapies (Housman et al. 2014), so the development of efflux pump or extrusion inhibitors is emerging as an alternative to assist in the treatment of this condition. Although various membrane transporter inhibitors have been found, none have been clinically successful, and the search to reverse MDR continues to focus primarily on natural products.

The use of medicinal preparations derived from plants has a long history, and by 2005, 57% of all drugs in clinical trials for cancer were natural products or their derivatives (Cragg and Newman 2005). In the case of MDR, natural products from diverse chemical origins, such as flavonoids, carotenoid glycosides, alkaloids, and terpenes, have been tested (Dewanjee et al. 2017). Among these, terpenes stand out as they have shown promising effects as MDR modulators, due to their low toxicity and their ability to function as substrates, inhibitors, or suppressors of the transcription of genes encoding membrane transporters in cancer cells (Wink 2012). Therefore, in this review, a systematic search was conducted for studies on human breast cancer cell lines using terpenes and their synthetic derivatives as chemoreversers, relying mainly on databases such as Google Scholar, PubMed, Scopus, and Scielo. The techniques implemented and the results obtained by the different study groups were analyzed and categorized throughout the review.

METHODS

This review was conducted using data collected from reputable databases, including PubMed, ScienceDirect, Springer, and Elsevier journals. The data was obtained from research and review articles focused on the use of terpenes of plant origin to overcome resistance to chemotherapy in breast cancer. These articles were summarized to create a comprehensive and advanced review on the role of terpenes in overcoming multidrug resistance (MDR) in breast cancer. Databases were searched using the following keywords: drug resistance, breast cancer, terpenes, P-gp, MRP1, BCRP, and chemotherapy. It

was verified that the articles considered for this review have been published until 2020.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Resistance to Multiple Drugs and Mechanisms of Action

The development of MDR during the course of chemotherapy has been considered a major obstacle in cancer treatment. Over the past three decades, the biological causes underlying MDR have been extensively studied and attributed to various molecular mechanisms. As mentioned previously, the existence of resistant malignant tumors in the breasts is very common among women. These tumors generally consist of mixed populations of malignant cells, some of which are sensitive to anticancer drugs, while others are resistant (Jonathan 2000). In this context, cells become resistant through different mechanisms, dependent or independent of the applied chemotherapy. These drugs only manage to eliminate the non-resistant cells, leaving a greater proportion of resistant cells in the body, which, as they multiply and the tumor begins to grow again, cause the regression of the cancer, as shown in Figure 1. In such cases, the majority of the tumor is already resistant, and the previously applied chemotherapy commonly fails, leading to extended treatments and increased dosages.

It has been demonstrated that MDR develops through various mechanisms, such as inhibition of cell death, drug inactivation, DNA damage, alteration of the drug target, and epigenetic modifications. In addition to these factors, different studies have suggested other mechanisms, including altered cell cycle checkpoint and cell cycle arrest, increased drug flux by transporters, and sequestration of anticancer drugs in lysosomes and other intercellular vesicles (Saraswathy and Gong 2013; Gillet and Gottesman 2010). MDR is classified according to the stage at which its appearance is visible; it can be intrinsic or extrinsic. In the case of intrinsic MDR, the cells exhibit resistance to chemotherapy due to their inherent genetic characteristics, while in extrinsic MDR, genetic alterations are attributed to exposure to

chemotherapy. The latter is the most problematic form of MDR, as it leads to chemotherapy failure, even after escalation of antitumor doses to toxic levels. In the case of intrinsic MDR, no detection methods are employed, and drugs that can reverse or prevent it in conjunction with chemotherapy have not been used in clinical practice, further complicating its treatment and diagnosis.

Of all the multiresistance mechanisms reported to date, the most studied are those involving ABC transporters. Therefore, the search for inhibitors of these translocases will allow the development of substances that contribute to cancer treatment. In this review, some of the reported MDR mechanisms were categorized into two aspects: mechanisms not related to membrane transporters and those related to them.

Mechanisms Not Dependent on ABC Transporters

Although ABC transporters have commonly been the most studied, different investigations have related other cellular and molecular mechanisms of MDR that do not involve these transporters. One of them is the intratumoral heterogeneity that can be observed in many types of cancer, which can be attributable to several different factors occurring primarily at the cellular level. This implies a natural generation of variants with certain genetic, epigenetic, transcriptomic, and proteomic properties (Mansoori et al. 2015). The tumor microenvironment is also considered in the discussion on oncological drug resistance as the main reason for the relapse and incurability of various cancer types. This microenvironment is also essential for distant metastasis (Al-Akra et al. 2019).

While multidrug resistance is known to develop through a variety of molecular mechanisms within the tumor cell, many tend to converge toward the alteration of apoptotic signaling. The enzyme glucosylceramide synthase (GCS), responsible for the bioactivation of the proapoptotic mediator ceramide to a non-functional glucosylceramide moiety, is overexpressed in many types of MDR tumors and has been implicated in cell survival in the presence of

chemotherapy (Lu and Mahato 2009). The resistance of cancer cells against anticancer agents may also be due to genetic differences in the individual, especially in somatic tumor cells (Mansoori et al. 2015). Some mutations, such as the C3435T mutation in exon 26 of the MDR1 gene, have been reported to inhibit and reduce the absorption of antitumor drugs (Nakamura et al. 2002); however, DNA and RNA are not always involved in MDR where damage occurs. Recent studies on miRNA profiling have confirmed that these small molecules play an important role in the development of chemosensitivity or chemoresistance in different types of cancer (Liu et al. 2019).

Extrusion of antineoplastics from the cell is not the only mechanism by which a drug can be eliminated; abnormalities in lysosomal function, protein trafficking, and secretion have now been clearly identified (Chauhan et al. 2003). Additionally, there is a group of enzymes that play an important role in the detoxification of drugs, ionizing molecules, and electrophilic compounds in the cell; these are the GST enzymes, which increase drug resistance in cancer cells directly by detoxifying the drug (Mansoori et al. 2015).

Fig. 1. General MDR scheme

MDR may begin before intrinsic MDR chemotherapy and be seen at first exposure or may appear after extrinsic MDR drug exposure. In both cases the cells present similar changes. Chemotherapy eliminates sensitive cells while the resistant cells survive, remaining in a greater proportion. When they multiply and the tumor returns, this time the cells will be mostly resistant.

MDR and ABC Transporters

Cytotoxic agents can enter cells through the direction of the concentration gradient. However, the absorption of the drug into cells through the direction of a high concentration gradient occurs only through active transport (Clynes 2013).

The first time a connection between MDR and membrane transporters was observed was in 1970, when it was shown in Chinese hamster ovary cell lines that a 170 kD glycoprotein (P-gp) correlated with the degree of drug resistance in several cell lines (Juliano and Ling 1979). Evidence for its role in resistance to pleiotropic drugs was provided in 1982, when it was demonstrated that DNA from resistant cell lines conferred resistance to non-resistant lines (Debenham et al. 1982). After the isolation of P-gp, another member of the ABC transporter superfamily, MRP1, was discovered (Wu et al. 2019).

Since then, at least 49 structurally related transporters, collectively known as the ABC superfamily, have been identified and categorized into seven subfamilies. Of these, 16 are primarily involved in human diseases (Tarling et al. 2013). These transporters are composed of two ATP-binding cytoplasmic (ABC) domains and two transmembrane domains. From an evolutionary perspective, they are highly conserved, with high sequence homology among all members, especially those within a particular family (Linton 2007). In this context, P-gp, MDR1, and BCRP have been the most studied (Table 1).

Table 1. ABC Transporters and their characteristics.

Protein	Gene	Type of structure	Confers resistance to	Reference
P-glycoprotein (P-gp)	ABCB1	It is composed of two similar moieties and each half contains a transmembrane domain and an ATP-binding domain	Anthracenes, anthracyclines, podophyllotoxins, taxanes, and vinca alkaloids	(Loo y Clarke 2005)
Multidrug resistance protein 1 (MRP1)	ABCC1	Glutathione-S-pump conjugates (GS-X)	Anthracendione, anthracycline, epipodophyllotoxin, vinca alkaloids	(Piet et al. 2000).
The breast cancer resistance protein (BCRP)	ABCG2	Has a transmembrane domain and an ATP-binding domain and only functions after dimerization	Doxorubicin, camptothecin and mitoxantrone	(Nakanishi, y Ross 2012)

In 1998, Doyle et al. isolated a new ABC transporter from MCF-7/AdrVp cells and verified that its transfection into MCF-7 cells reproduced the MDR phenotype. The new transporter was named breast cancer resistance protein (BCRP) because it was isolated from resistant human breast cancer cells (Nakanishi and Ross 2012).

Currently, specific substrates for each transporter and the relationship between their overexpression and resistant genotypes have been identified. However, attempts to translate these transporters into clinical targets have so far been unsuccessful.

The more ABC transporters that are expressed in the cancer tissue, the lower the chances of effective results with chemotherapy. For example, a recent

study in children with acute myeloid leukemia found a strong association between patient relapse and the number of overexpressed ABC transporters, such as ABCA3, ABCB1, ABCC3, and ABCG2, in cancer cells (Bartholomae et al. 2016).

Breast Cancer Models

To evaluate the effectiveness of anticancer drugs, it is essential to use a viable test system that truly represents the disease as it appears in humans. Currently, the most used *in vitro* models include single- and multicellular lines, as well as stem cells. Willers et al. (2019) in their review addressed the different options for MDR models, emphasizing human-derived cell lines as a strong pillar in the screening of anticancer drugs. Furthermore, it is relatively easy to perform genetic manipulation of these cells, which can provide information about the genetic mutations that occur in cancer cells, thus correlating with tumor tissues (Ashraf et al. 2012). Essentially, *in vitro* approaches refine preclinical results before advancing to animal and human trials, reducing ethical concerns, time, and cost. However, models based on *in vitro* cell cultures also have certain drawbacks (Willers et al. 2019).

As mentioned previously, the first time the effect of MDR was observed in a human breast cancer cell line (MCF-7) was in 1979 (Juliano and Ling 1979). Nowadays, different assays have been proposed for the evaluation of MDR. The determination of P-gp protein levels can be performed using a Western-blot assay, but proliferation, cell viability, and cytotoxicity assays are generally used to measure the potency of chemoreverters. Assays that measure rhodamine 123 flux are frequently used to measure inhibition of ABC transporters. In addition to these types of assays, accumulation of fluorescent dyes and vesicular transport assays can also be utilized. One of the main drawbacks mentioned for the use of *in vitro* models in MDR is the lack of standardization of the methods and techniques used to induce resistance in cell lines. Consequently, results obtained from different laboratories are not always comparable and may be attributed to the type of chemotherapeutic drugs

used or the specific concentrations applied (Willers et al. 2019). Due to this, *in vitro* studies in breast cancer should be considered as preliminary and informative studies that give rise to future investigations of promising drugs. Thanks to their low cost, easy handling, and proliferation time, they continue to be widely used in the field. The inability to accurately extrapolate to humans has contributed to the design of cell co-cultures, which are intended to better reproduce the primary elements of MDR, such as intracellular communications that better resemble the *in vivo* microenvironment (Griffith and Swartz 2006; Willers et al. 2019).

Terpenes as MDR Modulators

Despite continued efforts to treat multidrug resistance, no success has been found in clinical practice. There are multiple reasons for the timely failure of various drugs, such as toxicity, lack of solid preclinical data, choice of appropriate model, interference with the pharmacokinetics of chemotherapeutic drugs, and lack of specificity of inhibitors towards the ABC transporters (Choi and Yu 2014). Therefore, MDR modulators, also called chemosensitizers, that inhibit the activity of membrane transporters and enhance the cytotoxicity of conventional chemotherapy are important means to overcome MDR, and research has concentrated on these to reverse MDR in breast cancer.

P-gp inhibitors have different disadvantages; for example, verapamil and cyclosporine have not been successful, as poor elimination and metabolism made these agents too toxic for clinical application (Leopoldo et al. 2019).

In this review, we will discuss naturally occurring compounds that have been explored as modulators of MDR, mainly inhibitors of the membrane transporters described above.

The use of specialized metabolites obtained from different organisms, such as plants, has helped double our life expectancy in the 20th century. They have revolutionized medicine, given that their chemical diversity is co-related with biological and

genetic diversity. Currently, not only is there a wide variety of natural products, but thanks to technological and scientific advances, there are now many tools that enable the total synthesis of these types of compounds, as well as the creation of semi-synthetic derivatives to optimize their bioactivity as possible drugs (Riaz 2018).

Among the natural products used for pharmacological purposes, terpenoids stand out because they constitute the largest and most diverse class of natural products. Derived from five-carbon isoprene units assembled and modified in thousands of ways, they can be classified based on the number of isoprene units in the original structure, such as monoterpenoids (C10), sesquiterpenoids (C15), diterpenoids (C20), sesterterpenoids (C25), triterpenoids (C30), tetraterpenes (C40), and polyterpenes. Terpenes can be found in all classes of living organisms, and a large number of terpenoids with antibacterial, antimalarial, antineoplastic, and other pharmaceutical functions have been reported (Brahmkshatriya and Brahmshatriya 2013).

The following sections of this review present results from *in vitro* studies conducted to explore the chemoreversal potential of terpenes and their semisynthetic analogues in human breast cancer. 63 studies were analyzed where terpenoids were used as MDR modulators, of which only 33 were used against human breast cancer cell lines (Table 2); the data were classified according to the type of terpenoid used.

Monoterpenes

Monoterpenes are components of essential oils. Being widely distributed in the plant kingdom, they are extensively used in cooking and human healthcare products. Studies have shown that both natural monoterpenes and their synthetic derivatives possess various pharmacological properties, including antifungal, antibacterial, antioxidant, anticancer, antiarrhythmic, antiaggregant, anesthetic, antinociceptive, anti-inflammatory, antihistamine, and antispasmodic activities. Monoterpenes also act as growth regulators, heat

and perspiration modulators, tumor inhibitors, oxidative phosphorylation inhibitors, insect repellents, feline and canine attractants, and antidiabetics (Koziol et al. 2014). In the study conducted by Ravizza (1994), the effects of linalool were tested on adenocarcinoma cell lines, MCF-7 WT and MCF-7/AdrR, which are resistant to doxorubicin (DOX). The results show that linalool moderately inhibits cell proliferation and, at subtoxic concentrations, potentiates DOX-induced cytotoxicity. It was also able to induce a decrease in Bcl-xL levels.

Ascaridol is the active principle of the American worm seed *Chenopodium anthelminticum* L. Its activity was analyzed against the MDA-MB-231 cell line and its resistant counterpart that differentially expresses the MRP1 and BCRP genes, respectively. The findings indicate that ascaridol exerts antineoplastic activity (Efferth 2002).

Sesquiterpenes

Sesquiterpenes are lipophilic compounds. Biosynthesis in plants occurs through farnesyl pyrophosphate in the endoplasmic reticulum, and they consist of a 15-carbon skeleton, although their structure is diverse, the majority and the most functional forms are cyclic (Chadwick et al. 2013).

Jung et al. (2010) worked with 3 sesquiterpenoids (Caryophyllene-1,9 β -diol, clovane-2 β , 9a-diol, and (8R,9R)- β -caryophyllene oxide) isolated from the pods of *Sindora sumatrana* Miq. (Leguminosae), where (8R,9R)- β -caryophyllene oxide had a significant decrease in daunomycin efflux. A new sesquiterpene was isolated from the fruits of *Torilis japonica*, which turned out to be torylin. Torylin potentiates the cytotoxicities of adriamycin, colchicine, vinblastine, and taxol against multidrug-resistant cells (Kim et al. 1998).

Sesquiterpene coumarins have gained recent importance in the study of MDR reversal, as is the case with drimano-type sesquiterpene coumarins extracted from the fruits of *F. gummosa*. The effects of the isolated compounds were tested on P-gp-

mediated MDR in the MCF-7/Dox cell line, highlighting the dose-dependent effect of conferone, mogoltacin, and feselol. At 25 μ M, all sesquiterpene coumarins tested restored at least 50% of baseline uptake, but at 10 μ M, their potency varied, with conferone showing the highest potency and feselol the lowest (Iranshahi et al. 2014). Other sesquiterpene coumarins were isolated by Hanafi-Bojd et al. (2011), who investigated the MDR modulatory potential of galbanic acid (from the roots of *Ferula szowitsiana*) and farnesiferol A (from the roots of *Ferula persica*) on P-gp functionality using the rhodamine 123 flux assay in the doxorubicin-resistant MCF7/Adr cell line. Compared to verapamil, galbanic acid significantly inhibited P-gp activity. In inhibiting the P-gp transporter, farnesiferol A (0.5 μ g/ml) was more potent than verapamil at 15 minutes of exposure. The results indicate that plant-derived sesquiterpene coumarins may be promising candidates to be considered for future studies on the reversal of the multidrug resistance phenotype in the chemotherapy of cancer patients.

The bicyclic sesquiterpene esters of p-hydroxybenzoate of jaeschkeanadiol, isolated from the active fraction of the Egyptian medicinal plant *Ferula hermonis*, exerted a strong cytotoxic effect towards the MCF7 cell line and moderate activities towards other cell lines. However, it only showed good modulation of MDR in the CEM/ADR5000 cell line (leukemia cells) (Kuetel et al. 2014).

Diterpenes

By 2002, 10,541 diterpenoid compounds had already been reported (Chapman and Hall 2002), and it is also one of the groups that has been most studied as modulators of multidrug resistance in breast cancer, exhibiting other significant biological properties. The chemistry of bioactive diterpenes, especially the synthesis, has attracted much attention to obtain these compounds (Banerjee et al. 2008). In this section of the review, the results of different groups that studied the activity of diterpenes and their derivatives against resistant human breast cancer cells are presented.

The clerodane-type diterpenes from *Sindora sumatrana* have been potent modulators of MDR in breast cancer cells. (+)-7-acetoxy-15,16-epoxycleroda-3,13(16),14-trien-18-oic acid showed a strong inhibitory effect on P-gp, as great as that of verapamil. It enhanced the accumulation of daunomycin more than fourfold and significantly decreased the efflux, resulting in a decrease in the IC50 value (Jung et al. 2010). Ayhan et al. (1999) evaluated 10 diterpenes isolated from the roots of *Salvia hypargeia*, a plant endemic to Turkey, testing them on a vinblastine-resistant breast cancer cell line, with taxodione being the most active. The myrsinol derivative named J196-9-4 at concentrations of 5 and 10 μ M significantly reversed resistance to daunorubicin, vincristine, and topotecan. It competitively inhibited P-gp-mediated efflux and stimulated ATP hydrolysis (Chen et al. 2016).

Salvia amarissima is a plant from which various diterpenes with MDR modulating activity have been extracted in different phenotypes of breast cancer cells resistant to vinblastine, including amarysolide F (an acylated diterpenoid glucoside), amarissinin A, amarissinin B, and teotihuacanine. The latter was the most potent in reversing MDR, followed by amarysolide F, while amarissinins A and B had weak activity, compared to the control (reserpine) (Bautista et al. 2016; Bautista et al. 2015; Frago et al. 2019).

Ten new and seventeen known diterpenoids were isolated from *Scutellaria barbata*. These were tested in adriamycin-resistant breast cancer cells, and the neo-clerodane diterpenoids (scutebatin A, 6,7-di-O-nicotinoylscutebarbatine G, 6-O-nicotinoyl-7-O-acetylscutebarbatin G, scutebarbatin W) showed a reversal of the MDR in these cells, with scutebatin A being the most potent. Mechanistic investigations showed that it causes the suppression of P-gp activity and the restriction of its expression (Gui-Min et al. 2016). The two symmetric dimers of the ent-kaurane diterpenoid (crotonkinins C and D) from the leaves of the endemic Vietnamese medicinal plant *Croton tonkinensis* were also described and tested against MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cell lines, as

well as MCF-7 lines resistant to tamoxifen and adriamycin, finding that crotonkinin D has potent cytotoxic activity against all 4 cell lines (Phuong et al. 2012).

Labdane-type diterpenoids, galanals A and B, isolated from the Cameroonian spice *Aframomum arundinaceum*, showed moderate cytotoxicity toward resistant breast adenocarcinoma MDA-MB-231/BCRP cells (Kuede et al. 2014). On the other hand, *Marsdenia tenacissima*, a traditional Chinese medicinal herb used clinically for cancer treatment, had polyoxypregnanes isolated from the plant that were found active against MRP1 and BCRP in breast cancer cells (Kenneth et al. 2017).

Since 1994, 65 diterpenes have been isolated from 11 species of Euphorbia (Vasas et al. 2012). During this review, it was found that there is a considerable amount of diterpenes isolated from species of the genus Euphorbia, which share unique structural similarities. As an example, there is the study by Rui et al. (2018), where they isolated 15 jatrophane-type diterpenes from Euphorbia sororia, which were evaluated in MCF-7/ADR cells overexpressing P-gp. Eight compounds showed chemoreversal capabilities compared to verapamil, with the most potent compound, Euphosorphane A, possessing many advantages, including high potency in reversing P-gp-mediated resistance, low cytotoxicity, and inhibition of P-gp-mediated Rhodamine 123 (Rh123) efflux.

In 2009, Wei et al. managed to isolate two new diterpenes from *Euphorbia lathyris* and tested them, along with 4 other diterpenes, against MCF-7/ADM cells, which turned out to be powerful modulators of MDR. The relationship between their structure and biological activity was discussed from the aspect of different skeletons, and modulators of 5 types were proposed (jokinol, isolatirol, epoxylatyrol, 7-hydroxylatyrol, latirol). Six years later, they described the Euphorbia L 3 factor, a lathyrol-type diterpene, and they also designed five series of 37 new derivatives. These were evaluated *in vitro* using a chemoreversion assay and the Rh123 accumulation assay, where derivatives 19 and 25, as well as factor

L3, were the most powerful modulators of MDR (Wei et al. 2015).

The phytochemical study of *Pedilanthus tithymaloides* led to the isolation of 13 diterpenoids with a jatrophane carbon skeleton, and 22 new derivatives were synthesized. Activity was evaluated in the adriamycin-resistant cell line MCF-7/ADR. Compounds 19, 25, and 26 were identified as potent MDR modulators with greater MDR modulating capacity and less cytotoxicity than tariquidar. Compound 26 exhibited remarkable metabolic stability *in vitro* and a favorable antitumor *effect in vivo* (Jianyong et al. 2016).

Ten jatrophane backbone-based diterpenes, including rearranged polycyclic derivatives, were studied in the MDA-MB-231 (HTB-26) cell line to test MDR1- and MRP-mediated MDR reversal and carboxyfluorescein accumulation. Most of the jatrophanes tested enhanced the accumulation of the carboxyfluorescein indicator, and the results can be compared with the positive control, indomethacin. The case of pubescene B was greater than the control (53%), being the most potent compound. In a functional assay, where the accumulation of rhodamine 123 and verapamil was measured, only MRP was active, while MDR1 was inactive (Ferreira et al. 2005).

Technology has advanced to the point that natural sources are currently being replaced by the total synthesis of the compounds, as was the case in the study done by Schnabel et al. (2011), where the total synthesis of natural and unnatural jatrophane-5,12-dienes was carried out. Members of the set of natural and unnatural synthetic jatrophanes were subsequently examined as modulators of the efflux proteins P-gp, BCRP, and MRP1. The cell line used was MCF-7, and only diterpenes S9 and S10 were able to significantly inhibit MRP1 efflux, while only 33–35 significantly affected BCRP transport activity. Subsequent biological studies demonstrated that the most potent compound 33 of this collection possesses an MDR-reversing potency comparable to that of verapamil. Compound 2 (3-epi-characiol)

appeared to inhibit P-gp, which represented a promising avenue for the development of selective P-gp inhibitors.

Triterpenes

Triterpenes are structurally diverse secondary metabolites, characterized by a basic skeleton modified in multiple ways, allowing the formation of more than 20,000 known members. Triterpenoids are synthesized from isopentenyl diphosphate to generate squalene as a 30-carbon intermediate. Triterpenoids are found throughout nature, for example in fungi, different types of plants, animals, and marine organisms. They can be classified according to the number of carbocycles present, such as tetracyclics (grouping dammaranes, lanostanes, cycloartans, cucurbitanes, tirucallanes, and meliacans) and pentacyclics (where oleananes, ursanes, lupanes, and friedelanes are found) (Yan et al. 2014).

Triterpenes can exist in free or glycosylated form; the latter being called triterpene saponins. An example of these compounds is saikosaponin D (SSd), derived from *Bupleurum chinense* DC, which has anti-inflammatory, anti-infectious, and antitumor properties. Li et al. (2017) aimed to investigate the MDR reversal effect of saikosaponin D in adriamycin-resistant MCF-7 cells. SSd increased the cytotoxicity of ADR in MCF-7/ADR cells, and the resistance of SSd treatment was shown to be significantly higher compared to the untreated group, inhibiting P-gp-mediated drug flux. Another saponin studied is Paris saponin VII (PSVII), extracted from *Trillium tschonoskii* Maxim, which was evaluated in the breast cancer cell line MCF-7/ADR, finding that through the inhibitory activity of P-gp, the induction of apoptosis was achieved in the breast cancer cell line (Li et al. 2014).

Shan et al. (2011) investigated the proliferation-inhibiting and apoptosis-inducing effects of ursolic acid (UA) and oleanolic acid (OA) on multidrug-resistant breast cancer cells. They found that both UA and OA showed significant inhibition in a time- and concentration-dependent manner. The effects of UA were better than those of OA in inhibiting cell growth.

Asiaticoside (ATS), a triterpene extracted from *Centella asiatica* (L.) Urban, a traditional Chinese herb, has a good healing effect due to its stimulation of collagen synthesis. The induction of apoptosis in cancer cells and the increase in vincristine (VCR) cytotoxicity by the action of asiaticoside were examined. Its MDR inhibitory potential combined with vincristine on the proliferation of several cancer cell lines, including MCF-7/ADM, was evaluated. They found that asiaticoside, as a biochemical modulator, can induce apoptosis and enhance the antitumor activity of vincristine in cancer cells, and could be useful in cancer chemotherapy (Huang et al. 2004).

Yao et al. (2017) isolated four abeo-type limonoids, five cedrelone-type limonoids, and five walsurin-type limonoids from the fruits of *Walsura robusta*, along with 21 known compounds. Among the results, walsurin A showed a significant effect in the sensitization of these resistant cancers at non-toxic concentrations in MCF-7/DOX cells, possibly due to inhibition of P-gp. Pan et al. (2016) investigated whether Alisol F 24 acetate (ALI) could reverse the MDR of MCF-7/DOX cells. ALI showed a significant and concentration-dependent cytotoxic effect in combination with doxorubicin by increasing intracellular accumulation and inducing nuclear migration of doxorubicin. Furthermore, ALI also promoted early apoptosis in a time-dependent manner. These results suggest that ALI may improve the chemosensitivity of doxorubicin and strengthen its anticancer effect. Steroids are bis-nor-triterpenes based on the cyclopentanoperhydrophenanthrene ring system. Cucurbitacin B (CuB), a natural steroid-type anticancer compound found in the *Cucurbitaceae* family, reversed MDR and reduced CIP2A expression in MCF-7/Adr cells. CuB treatment also induced caspase-dependent apoptosis and a decrease in Akt phosphorylation. Suppression of Akt phosphorylation was mediated by CuB-induced activation of protein phosphatase 2A (PP2A). In conclusion, they found that enhancement of PP2A activity by CIP2A inhibition promotes CuB-induced MDR reversal (Cai et al. 2016).

Fig. 2. Diversity of modulating terpenes and structural similarities

Terpenes constitute the largest and most diverse class of natural products, there are structural similarities highlighted here between the different modulating terpenes such as macrocycles and aromatic hydrocarbons. (A) Linalool, (B) ascaridol, (C) Farnesiferol A, (D) Conferone, (E) Toryllin, (F) Euphorbia factor L 3, (G) Euphosorpane A, (H) Pubescence B, (I) Teotihuacanin, (J) Walsurin A, (K) Alisol F 24, (L) Cucurbitacin B, (M) Lycopene, (N) Lycopene.

Tetraterpenes

From a chemical perspective, carotenoids are tetraterpenes composed of multiple isoprene units. Different carotenoids have been tested as modulators of MDR. Gyémánt et al. (2006) analyzed the function of the MDR1 protein through the accumulation of the drug R123 in the MCF-7 cell line in the presence of carotenoids, among which (13Z)-zeaxanthin was able to improve the antiproliferative effect in combination with epirubicin.

Carotenoids, isolated from paprika and other vegetables, were analyzed for their effect on Rhodamine 123 accumulation in MDA-MB-231 (HTB-26) cells. Apoptosis was induced in the presence of lycopene, zeaxanthin, and capsanthin. The data suggest the potential of carotenoids as potential resistance modifiers in cancer chemotherapy (Molnar et al. 2004).

CONCLUSIONS

Since 1979, when the first resistant MCF-7 cell line was obtained, the use and development of resistant phenotypes has continued widely, as seen in Table 2, where in 26 of 33 studies, the MCF-7 cell line was used in its different multidrug-resistant phenotypes, such as adriamycin, doxorubicin, vinblastine, taxol, colchicine, daunorubicin, vincristine, topotecan, epirubicin, and mitoxantrone, with the doxorubicin and adriamycin-resistant phenotypes being the most used. Thanks to the variety of phenotypes resistant to different drugs, their accessibility, and easy handling, the MCF-7 cell line is the most used *in vitro* MDR model.

As previously mentioned, the main problem with common reversers is their toxicity, such as verapamil, which has not been effective in subtoxic doses. Therefore, we are looking for MDR modulators that are less toxic for the body in general, and this is where terpenes have stood out due to being non-toxic and the diversity of their structures (Figure 2). There is still a large number of terpenes that have not been tested in MDR, while studies have focused mainly on diterpenes (Table 2), which provides a broader

overview of the possibilities in the search for MDR modulators.

The main molecular target of terpenes is P-gp (Table 2), however, not much is still known about the structural relationship and type of specific activity of terpenes as MDR modulators (Jianyong et al. 2016). Structure-activity relationship (SAR) studies have shown that the saturated five-membered ring was important for the activity. Meanwhile, Schnabel et al. (2011) found that compounds having a larger aromatic substituent at C-3 possessed inhibitory activity, while the presence of the smaller benzoyl residue at C-3 was not sufficient. Knowing how the chemical structure of terpenes interacts with ABC transporters could solve the problem of MDR in cancer, by finding non-toxic modulators that can be used clinically.

Plants are the most abundant source of MDR reverters, and among these, the species of the *Euphorbiaceae* family stand out throughout this review for the large number of diterpenes that have been isolated and tested as modulators of MDR. Additionally, some plant species such as *Salvia amarissima* have been found as important sources of potent chemoreverters. In the case of sesquiterpenes, plants of the genus *Ferula* have been studied on more than one occasion in the search for chemoreverters.

Further clinical studies are warranted to fully explore the therapeutic potential of terpenes and integrate them into treatment protocols, which could revolutionize the management of breast cancer and improve patient survival rates.

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Table 2. Terpene Studies in Human Resistant Breast Cancer Cell Lines

Terpene name	Source	Transporters Involved	Cell Line	Test Chemotherapeutic Agent	Interaction Mechanism	Reference
Monoterpenes						
Linalol	-	P-gp	MCF7 WT y MCF7 adrr	Doxorubicin	Induces a decrease in Bcl-xl levels.	Ravizza. (1994)
Ascaridol	<i>Chenopodium anthelminticum L.</i>	P-gp, BCRP y MPR1	MDA-MB-231	-	-	Efferth 2002
Sesquiterpenes						
B-Caryophyllene (8R,9R)-oxide	<i>Sindora sumatrana Miq. (Leguminosae),</i>	-	MCF/7	Daunomycin	Not described	(Jung et al. 2010);
Torylin	<i>Torilis japonica</i>	-	MCF7 / ADR	Adriamycin, vinblastine, taxol and colchicine	Not described	(kim et al. 1998)
Conferone, mogoltacin and feselol	<i>F. Gummosa</i>	P-gp	MCF-7 / Dox	Doxorubicin	Inhibition of p-gp	(Iranshahi et al. 2014)
Galbanic acid	<i>Ferula szowitsiana</i>	P-gp	MCF7 / Adr	Doxorubicin	Not described	(Hanafi-Bojd et al. 2011)
Farnesiferol A	<i>Ferula prsica</i>	P-gp	MCF7 / Adr	Doxorubicin	Not described	(Hanafi-Bojd et al. 2011)
Jaeschkeanadiol P-hydroxybenzoate	<i>Ferula hermonis</i>	-	MCF7	-	-	(Kuete et al 2014)
Diterpenes						
J196-9-4	<i>Euphorbia prolifera</i>	P-gp	MCF-7	Daunorubicin, vincristine and topotecan	Competitive P-gp inhibitor.	(Chen et al. 2016)
(+) - 7-acetoxy-15,16-epoxycleroda-3,13 (16), 14-trien-18-oic acid	<i>Sindora sumatrana</i>	P-pgp	MCF/7	Daunomycin	Not described	(Jung et al. 2010);
Taxodione	<i>Salvia hypargeia</i>	P-gp	BC 1	Vinblastine	Not described	(Ayhan et al. 1999)
Amarisolida F	<i>Salvia amarissima</i>		MCF-7	Vinblastine	-	(fragoso et al. 2019)
Scutebatina A	<i>Scutellaria barbata</i>	P-gp	MCF-7	Adriamycin	Suppression of P-gp activity and restriction of expression	(Gui-Min et al. 2016)

Euphorbia factor L 7a and Euphorbia factor L 2	<i>Euphorbia lathyris</i>	P-gp	MCF-7	Adriamycin	P-gp inhibition	(Wei et al. 2009)
Crotonquinone D	<i>Crotón tonkinensis</i>	P-gp	MCF-7 y MDA-MB-231	Tamoxifen and adriamycin	Inhibition of p-gp by the hydroxy group at C-18	(Phuong et al. 2012)
Galanals A and B	<i>Aframomum arundinaceum,</i>	BCRP	MDA-MB-231 / BCRP	-	-	(Kwete et al 2014)
Euphorbia factor L 3 and derivatives 19 and 25	<i>Euphorbia lathyris</i>	P-gp	MCF-7	Adriamycin	Inhibition of p-gp relation with hydrophobic interactions and hydrogen bonds in the flexible cavity of P-gp	(Wei et al. 2015)
Euphosorophane A	<i>Euphorbia sororia</i>	P-gp	MCF-7	Doxorubicin	P-gp inhibition	(Rui et al. 2018)
Compound 26 (-9,15-Phyacetoxy-3,7-dibenzoyloxy-1,13,14-trihydroxyatropa-5 E-ene)	<i>Pedilanthus tithymaloides</i>	P-gp	MCF-7	Adriamycin	Inhibition related to lipophilicity	(Jianyong et al. 2016)
Pubescene B	<i>Euphorbia pubescens</i>	MDR1 y MRP	MDA-MB-231 (HTB-26)	Identification using monoclonal antibodies and carboxyfluorescein	MDR1 inactivation	(Ferreira et al. 2005)
Compounds 33, S9, S10 and 2 (3-epi-characiol)	<i>Síntesis total</i>	P-gp, BCRP y MPR1	MCF-7	Calcein-AM accumulation assays	Inhibition of transporters by larger aromatic substituent at C-3.	(Schnabel et al. 2011)
Polioxypregnanes COP	<i>Marsdenia tenacissimaes</i>	BCRP y MPR1	MCP-7 / VP MCF-7 / FLV1000	Doxorubicin and mitoxantrone	Inhibition of ABC transporters by molecular docking	(Kenneth et al. 2017)
Teotihuacanine	<i>Salvia amarissima</i>	P-GP	MCF-7	Vinblastine	Not described	(Bautista et al. 2015)
Triterpenes						
Saikosaponin D	<i>Bupleurum chinense</i>	P-gp	MCF-7	Adriamycin	P-gp inhibition	(Li et al. 2017)
Saponin of Paris VII	<i>Trillium tschonoskii Maxim</i>	P-gp	MCF-7	Adriamycin	Reduced P-gp expression	(Li et al. 2014)
Asiaticoside	<i>Centella asiática (L.) Urban</i>	-	MCF-7	Vincristine	Not described	(Huang et al. 2004)
Ursolic acid and oleanolic acid	-	-	MCF-7	Adriamycin	Possible transcription suppressors of genes related to apoptosis and MDR.	(Shan et al. 2011)

Walsurin A	<i>Walsura robusta</i>	P-gp	MCF-7	Doxorubicin	Inhibition of P-gp function	(Yao et al. 2017)
Alisol F 24	<i>Rhizoma alismatis</i>	P-gp	MCF-7	Doxorubicin	DOX nuclear accumulation	Pan et al. 2016)
Cucurbitacin B	<i>Cucurbitaceae</i>	-	MCF-7 / Adr	Doxorubicin	Reduced CIP2A expression	(Cai et al. 2016)

Tetraterpenes

(13Z)-Zeaxanthin	<i>Lycium halimifolium</i>	P-GP	MCF-7	Epirubicin.	Possible division in the hydrophobic core of the membrane and cause a decrease in the fluidity of lipids.	(Gyémánt et al. 2006)
Lycopene	<i>Lycopersicon esculentum</i>	P-gp	MDA MB 231 (HTB-26)	Fluorescence flow test	They form charge transfer complexes with p-gp	(Molnar et al. 2004)
Zeaxanthin	<i>Lycium halimifolium</i>	P-gp	MDA MB 231 (HTB-26)	Fluorescence flow test	They form charge transfer complexes with p-gp	(Molnar et al. 2004)
Capsanthin	<i>Capsicum annum</i>	P-gp	MDA MB 231 (HTB-26)	Fluorescence flow test	They form charge transfer complexes with p-gp	(Molnar et al. 2004)